

LOW COST COCKPIT SIMULATORS FOR EVALUATING NEW CONTROL/DISPLAY CONCEPTS

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Summary

This paper discusses development of two inexpensive cockpit simulators for evaluating advanced control/display devices and concepts. One cockpit simulator is tailored for evaluation of prototype control/display hardware including light emitting diode displays, liquid crystal displays, 3D stereoscopic displays, and head tracking devices. The second cockpit simulator described utilizes large area reconfigurable CRT displays. This "reconfigurable" cockpit was first used to conduct evaluations of control/display concepts for the in-house portion of Wright Lab's ICAAS (Integrated Controls and Avionics for Air Superiority) program. Discussion of both cockpits includes hardware composition, simulation capabilities and evaluations conducted in each cockpit.

Introduction

The value of simulation in research is indisputable. Ideas can be quickly prototyped and subjectively or objectively evaluated. Those ideas deemed useful are pursued and the others discarded. However, the cost of simulation can be exorbitant.

In Wright Laboratory's Flight Dynamics Directorate, Cockpit Integration Division (identified by Air Force code letters as FIP), simulation is used to evaluate display and control devices that could prove valuable to current and future Air Force cockpits. FIP also evaluates informational display formats and pilot aiding concepts in a simulated mission-oriented environment. While using simulation as an evaluation methodology, FIP strives to control the cost of simulation. Simulation requirements are determined by the research to be undertaken. From these requirements, cockpit simulators are designed and built to the required level of sophistication. This paper discusses two cockpit simulators used in FIP, each developed for specific evaluation capabilities and each controlling costs in similar and unique ways. These cockpit simulators, MAGIC and Manned Combat Station, will be discussed in the following two sections.

MAGIC

MAGIC (Microprocessor Applications For Graphics and Interactive Communications) is a generic single-seat fighter

cockpit simulator. Used as a research tool in our Advanced Crew-Tailored Cockpit Concepts Laboratory, it hosts the evaluations of new display formats and technologies with emphasis on pilot workload reduction. This research is targeted for integration into aircraft approximately ten years into the future. MAGIC's design provides a cockpit environment which maintains experimental consistency, particularly with respect to the position of the controls and displays relative to a pilot.

MAGIC's capabilities and flexibilities result from its composition. It is supported by a large number of peripheral devices, each offering specialized capabilities. The primary factor helping the MAGIC cockpit simulator control cost is the use of these devices, most of which are low cost, off-the-shelf items. The physical elements comprising the MAGIC simulator are discussed in the next section.

Physical Components

The physical components integrated to derive the MAGIC simulator consist of the cockpit, computers, and other peripheral equipment.

The cockpit consists of the shell and seat, front panel and displays, and various controls. The cockpit shell is constructed from plywood. The front panel, illustrated in figure 1, contains five monitors. Three are stacked vertically, the lowest CRT being mounted slightly above a pilot's knees.

The other two monitors are located to the left and right of the center CRT. The top monitor is used to simulate the Head Up Display (HUD). This CRT is a 16 inch multisync, high resolution (1280 x 1024 pixels) Mitsubishi monitor. Its frequency range also gives it the capability of displaying 120 hz stereoscopic 3D images. The other four monitors are 12 inch NTSC compatible and are used to simulate multifunctional displays. The left and right monitors are modified Magnavox televisions. The center and bottom monitors were manufactured by Tektronix.

The MAGIC cockpit contains various controls and input devices allowing sufficient pilot interaction with the simulation.

Figure 1 - MAGIC Cockpit

Active controls contained in the cockpit are an A-7 aircraft throttle and a Measurement Systems force stick. Supporting switches found on the throttle include a speedbrake and a communications switch. Active switches found on the force stick include a weapons release button, trigger and a pitch trim switch. The cockpit also contains twelve programmable display pushbuttons (PDP). A bank of four PDPs are located beneath the left, center, and right monitors. The PDPs are pixel addressable light emitting diode displays capable of displaying pictorial formats as well as alphanumeric characters. A bank of four tricolor switches are located below the HUD monitor. Like the PDPs, these are also pixel addressable and very flexible in use. The center and bottom monitors have touch sensitive overlays allowing the pilot to interact with displayed formats.

Six computers are used to support the simulation: five personal computers and one graphics workstation. MAGIC's reliance on personal computers is one of the primary factors in making MAGIC a low-cost simulator. The responsiveness of the simulation (e.g., allowing a 30hz aeromodel update rate) is a testimony to the processing power provided by personal computers. Three 386 Compaq personal computers and one 486 Dell personal computer satisfy the majority of MAGIC's computational needs. They are responsible for running an F-16 Block 5 aircraft aeromodel and other programs as well as servicing analog inputs from the stick and throttle, digital inputs from the switches and RS-232 inputs from the touch sensitive overlays. All intercomputer communication is done via ethernet. The personal computers can also generate graphics on the four NTSC monitors in the cockpit. Each Compaq contains an AT&T Truevision TARGA graphics board which provides the cockpit with dynamic graphics capability. The TARGA boards can also be used to digitize images from laser discs also supporting MAGIC and then augment these images with overlaid graphics. The augmented images can be digitally stored to disc for later display.

MAGIC also uses a Silicon Graphics Iris 4D320VGX workstation to generate the HUD and stereographic displays. When necessary, all of the cockpit's NTSC monitors can be driven by shared Silicon Graphics computers located in the computer facility hosting MAGIC.

Most of the software is written in C. To minimize software development, the simulation environment software typically remains unchanged. Only device handling and graphics software are added or modified to meet the needs of specific evaluations. To achieve compatibility with the rest of the organization and therefore maximize reuse of software, newer software is being written in C++ using an object oriented design and development approach.

MAGIC utilizes peripheral devices to add flexibility and capability to the simulation environment. These devices are also used to achieve needed simulation performance. MAGIC's design heavily utilizes a distributed processing architecture. Each peripheral device is programmable and therefore runs independently, thus relieving the personal computers of additional processing requirements. Peripheral devices supporting the MAGIC cockpit simulator include laser disc players and a speech synthesis-recognition system.

Two Pioneer laser disc players are used in the simulation. Each disc can hold up to 42,000 NTSC video frames. The laser discs can be programmed to, on command, display a static image or a dynamic scene by sequencing through a series of frames. A typical use of these laser disc players is to give the pilot a preview of a target area. This allows the pilot to plan an attack or escape route although miles away from his strike point.

A Texas Instruments speech board hosted in a Z-248 personal computer is used to support speech recognition and synthesis in the MAGIC cockpit. The speech recognition system uses voice templates and therefore requires training. Once programmed with a particular pilot's templates, the pilot can use verbal commands to cause particular events to occur in the simulated aircraft's systems. Speech templates can be selectively activated to minimize recognition mistakes. Speech synthesis is also used. FIP chooses to play back digitally recorded speech to provide a natural as opposed to "machine-like" voice sound. Typically, this is used as caution advisory feedback, warning the pilot of existing aircraft system problems or of potential threats.

A window hosted software package, Generic Voice Interface, developed and distributed by the Cockpit Integration Division, is used to facilitate template generation.¹ This package is also used during simulation. It allows particular voice templates and synthesized phrases to be selectively activated. The run-time portion acts as a state machine, modifying the set of active templates and phrases as a result of particular cockpit stimulus or recognized command.

MAGIC's Simulation Environment

All four NTSC monitors simulate multifunctional displays (MFD). These displays are usually driven by either the TARGA boards or the Panasonic video disc players. The center MFD can be used to display a track map, a simple map showing the route the pilot must follow to complete his mission. It can also display digitized images of waypoints (landmarks such as roads and buildings) and expanded maps. The bottom monitor contains a look-down view of the target area. Pushing a PDP allows the target area to be displayed dynamically, graphically drawn in 3D perspective. This dynamic attribute allows the pilot to preview the target area as a simulated fly-by. The left monitor is used to display system formats including the fuel and weapons systems. The right monitor is also used to display system formats informing the pilot of engine, hydraulic or electrical system status. When simulated emergencies are introduced into the simulation, computerized checklists are displayed on the left monitor. As each element of the checklist is completed, that element's display color changes, allowing the pilot to look away and then return his attention to the next element requiring his attention.

Speech synthesis is used in a scenario simulating fuel tank damage. The simulated on-board computer verbally warns the pilot, supplying candidate solutions to fix the problem. The pilot can then verbally instruct the computer to handle the problem.

Experiments done in MAGIC

The MAGIC cockpit simulator hosts an average of five cockpit concept evaluations per year. Recently, evaluations have addressed Military Standard HUD symbology, Head Down Primary Flight Display symbology, stereoscopic 3D displays, and voice recognition.

The latest experiment conducted in MAGIC evaluated various methods for designating targets residing in a stereographic 3D volume.² A cursor resides in this volume which extends seven inches in front of the display to 15 inches behind the display. The 3D cursor and surrounding environment were created by combining stereographic displays with perspective graphics. Methods used to manipulate the cursor included imperative voice phrases, a four axis joystick, and an ultrasonic tracking device. Subjects were tasked to designate objects located within the display with the cursor. All three methods of cursor control were used by each subject. The graphic image had a consistent amount of clutter represented by mountains, railroad track, rivers, and power lines. Task difficulty varied by changing the position of the object(s) being designated and by changing the amount of clutter contained in the image. Additionally, various aiding algorithms for designating objects were also evaluated.

The cockpit provided a consistent, uniform experimental environment for conducting the evaluation. Consistency is especially important in stereographic evaluations as the distance between a subject's eyes and the display affect image disparity

and therefore the perceived stereographic effect. All images were displayed on MAGIC's HUD monitor. All three controlling devices were easily integrated into MAGIC's simulation environment.

MAGIC In Summary

MAGIC controls its simulation costs by integrating commercially available off-the-shelf components into the cockpit simulation. The peripheral devices used supply most of MAGIC's capabilities and flexibilities. Its distributed architecture provides sufficient simulation responsiveness while also serving to minimize the complexity of the simulation.

Manned Combat Station

The Manned Combat Station (MCS) is a cockpit simulator located in FIP's Tactical Aircraft Cockpit Simulation (TACS) facility. MCS was designed to support objective evaluations of cockpit display and control concepts in a mission-oriented environment. MCS is a software reconfigurable, generic fighter cockpit utilizing a large CRT to create a virtual front panel in the cockpit. Its reconfigurable nature allows various display concepts to be easily compared. MCS was created to support mission-oriented evaluations in a low-cost manner.

Like MAGIC, the Manned Combat Station's physical construction contributes to keeping its cost of simulation down. However, design and development of the software is the primary factor helping control simulation cost. Its physical construction and software design will be discussed in the next two sections.

MCS Physical Components

The physical components of the MCS include the cockpit, its displays, controls, and supporting computers. The Manned Combat Station can be seen in figure 2.

The MCS cockpit consists of a cockpit shell, two monitors, a stick, throttle, and various input devices. The cockpit shell is constructed of plywood and contains an F-16 aircraft seat. The crewstation is approximately the size of an F-16 crew station. Mounted on the front of the cockpit, located just above the pilot's knees, is a 19 inch color CRT. This monitor hosts the aircraft simulator's head down displays (HDD) and an oversized up-front controller. Mounted above the head down display monitor is a 13 inch color monitor used to display a 40 degree field-of-view out-the-window scene and an 18 degree field-of-view HUD. Both displays are low cost, commercially available, off-the-shelf computer monitors. Like the MAGIC cockpit, MCS also provides a cockpit environment which maintains experimental consistency.

Figure 2 - Manned Combat Station

The pilot controls the MCS cockpit with an F-16-like, side mounted force stick and an F-15-like throttle mounted to the right and left of the pilot, respectively. The pilot interacts with the simulated aircraft's systems via HOTAS (hands on throttle and stick) switches, touch sensitive overlay mounted over the HDD monitor, and programmable display pushbuttons (PDPs). Using HOTAS controls, a pilot can manipulate a cursor across virtual head down displays. In combination, the cursor and the HOTAS controls can be used to perform a number of functions such as designating aircraft, manipulating sensor positions and selecting format options. A pilot can also interact with the virtual head down displays through the touch sensitive overlay. All functions accomplished with HOTAS and the cursor can be accomplished by touch. Eight PDPs are mounted on both the right and left sides of the HDD monitor. The PDPs are generally utilized for major mode (Air-to-Air, Navigation, etc.) selection.

The MCS uses three Silicon Graphics workstations to support its graphic and computational requirements. A Silicon Graphics 3130 is used to draw the HUD and out-the-window scene. One Silicon Graphics 4D 120 GTX is used to draw the reconfigurable head's down displays. Also, a Silicon Graphics 4D 340S (without graphics processing capability) is used to execute display/control logic and aeromodel processes. Two of these systems are sufficient to accommodate the graphics and processing required by the MCS. The 4D 340S is a central point for analog-to-digital input, digital input, and digital output for the TACS facility. Therefore, the 4D 340S is used to accomplish most of MCS processing requirements. Evaluations targeted for the MCS cockpit simulator dictated the requirement for the flexibility and power offered by these workstations. Selection of this type of system was the most cost-effective way of meeting the simulation's design requirements. Also, because several simulators are supported by FIP, these workstations can be shared helping amortize their cost.

Inter-computer communication is performed via ethernet

and a fiber optic shared memory network. Ethernet is utilized to remotely start up all processes by executing a restricted shell. Datagram or TCP protocols can be used to pass simulation data if necessary. However, SCRAMnet (a fiber optic shared memory network produced by Systran, Inc.) provides greater throughput and efficiency than ethernet as well as a more convenient method of moving data from system to system. SCRAMnet boards, located in each computer, add memory to each system. Data written to SCRAMnet memory is transmitted through a fiber optic network, causing the data to be present at the same memory location in all systems. SCRAMnet alleviates the need of packing and unpacking data as required by an ethernet communication modality. This fiber optic shared memory network supports the abstraction of an avionics data bus. This abstraction allows processes to retrieve necessary information, generated by other simulated systems, from dedicated bus locations.

MCS Software Components

The overall software composition of the Manned Combat Station is a collection of cooperating processes. Typically, each process simulates a significant system in an aircraft. This type of architecture has several important benefits, particularly with respect to controlling MCS's simulation cost. First, the collection of processes minimizes the simulation's complexity. A process need only know about those system details necessary for it to perform its specific function, and no more. Narrowing the scope of a particular process improves its understandability, therefore making it easier to maintain. Second, the architecture supports flexibility. Minimizing process implementation interdependence allows processes to be easily changed or replaced. This loosely coupled architecture supports change to the simulation without side-effects rippling throughout the rest of the system. A third benefit offered by the loosely coupled architecture is process scheduling flexibility. Scheduling can be determined by the needs of the specific system being modeled. For example, sophisticated aeromodel processes require more frequent updates as compared to a simulated electrical system. Having separate processes allows each to be scheduled appropriately.

All software is executed in a UNIX environment. UNIX interprocess communication primitives are used to support cooperation and data sharing between processes. All processes utilize UNIX interval timers for independent scheduling and interval timer signal handlers. As a result, most processes spend a predominant portion of a cycle "paused", waiting for the next cycle, thus freeing the processor for use by other processes.

MCS Simulation Environment

Unlike the MAGIC cockpit which receives its capabilities and flexibilities from peripheral devices, MCS derives its capabilities and flexibilities primarily from software. MCS does not rely on peripheral hardware but on software abstractions of aircraft systems. Because so much software is

necessary to support the MCS, efforts (such as those discussed in the previous section) are taken to control the cost of software development and maintenance.

MCS supports a rapidly reconfigurable Head Down Display. Up to three conventionally sized virtual displays have been hosted on this CRT plus an up-front controller. Pressing a PDP, a pilot can replace the three virtual displays with two proportionately larger virtual displays. Pressing the PDP again, the two virtual displays can be replaced by one proportionately larger virtual display.

Recalling that MCS hosts cockpit display and control evaluations in a mission oriented environment, along with the generation of the virtual front panel, a simulated mission environment must be supplied. The graphics software is analogous to the visible part of an iceberg. The graphics get most of the attention while most of the simulation is submerged from view. Some of MCS supporting abstractions are described in the following paragraphs.

Formats shown in each virtual display can be controlled by interacting with the display via the touch sensitive overlay. However, a throttle mounted castle switch allows the pilot to rotate through the most frequently used formats on each display. The throttle's castle switch controls four format queues, one for each virtual heads down display and one for the up-front controller. Each respective queue identifies the 3 formats most frequently used on that particular display when in a particular aircraft mode (such as Navigation or Air-to-Air). By displacing the castle switch off center (left changes left display, right changes right display, down changes center display, and up changes up-front-controller menu) formats displayed on virtual displays can be sequentially selected from the queue. Each queue contains only 3 formats, those considered the most relevant to the mission segment. The size of the format queues was a compromise between rapid advancement to any of the three important formats and easy access to a larger number of formats.

Datalink is another abstraction simulated in the MCS. Information available to the MCS cockpit can originate from other experimental entities such as other Blue (Air Force) aircraft, simulated AWACS aircraft, or a simulated JTIDS network. FIP has put substantial emphasis on utilizing datalinked information, particularly intra-flight datalink. All aircraft system information is distributed to all other flight aircraft via datalink. This includes all sensor information and track files. To manage this additional information another abstraction is modeled: Interneted Attack Management.

Interneted Attack Management assumes that the Blue aircraft have on-board pilot aiding computers which automatically assign and prioritize target aircraft to members of the Blue flight. Assignments and priorities are based on the Blue flight's mission, weapons status across the flight, and other factors. The Interneted Attack Management system also provides tactics guidance for the lead pilot of the Blue flight. Various tactics options are displayed and weighted with a

figure of merit. Tactics recommendations are based on the flight's mission, weapons, numbers of possible launches, and potential exposure to missile threats. If a particular tactic is accepted, the flight guidance systems across the Blue aircraft become coupled with the tactics system.

To complete the mission oriented run-time environment, digital aircraft are used. The digital aircraft can represent hostile, friendly, and unknown aircraft. All digital aircraft can be designated and launched on from the MCS cockpit. Hostile digital aircraft can be programmed to launch missiles based on several criteria at any member of the Blue flight.

When enemy missile launch is detected, MCS's simulated pilot aiding computers recommend missile evasion options. The pilot can choose to utilize the computer's suggested evasive maneuver by pulling back on a boat switch mounted on the side of the throttle. At this time, bank and G symbology are displayed on the HUD. The pilot can also attempt to evade the missile without displayed assistance.

The pilot can also control a cursor which resides on one of the three heads down displays or the up-front controller. The cursor is slued via a control mounted on the throttle. The cursor provide the pilot the ability to activate virtual format switches or designate aircraft and other objects of interest contained in any displayed format.

MCS Evaluations

The Manned Combat Station was used to conduct four evaluations for the ICAAS (Integrated Control and Avionics for Air Superiority) Advanced Development Program Office (ADPO).³ FIP supported the ICAAS ADPO performing evaluations addressing various pilot-vehicle interface issues. The use of the Manned Combat Station in two of these evaluations is described in the following paragraphs.

Comparison of the Visual Qualities of Display Formats. - This evaluation consisted of subjective evaluations of the display formats and the design concepts created from the Air-To-Air Attack Management program. The evaluation dealt primarily with the pilot-vehicle interface aspects of display formats, including the use of color, size and shape of display symbols, structure of menus, location of information elements within each format, adequacy of display information, and the need for additional display elements.

Comparison of Missile Launch Envelope Symbologies. - The effectiveness of several representations of missile launch envelopes were compared experimentally using Air-to-Air Attack Management formats. Pilots were instructed to watch the tactical situation and either fire, or break off depending on the situation. In addition, some mixed conditions provided redundant ownership missile launch information on the HUD in the form of either a thermometer or a countdown missile launch envelope. Missile Launch envelopes took the form of Rakes, Fans, or Launch Acceptability Regions on the HDD.

MCS in Summary

MCS is a cockpit simulator supported by a set of flexible, loosely coupled software processes. The physical components of the cockpit itself are simply inexpensive, off-the-shelf color monitors and recycled aircraft controllers and a seat. The primary cost of the MCS simulation is in software development and maintenance. By maintaining a reusable simulation environment, typically only control and display software need replaced from evaluation to evaluation.

Conclusion

The Cockpit Integration Division minimizes the cost of cockpit simulation by utilizing commercially available off-the-shelf monitors, computers, and graphics systems and by applying software design principles to create a software environment which is loosely coupled and reconfigurable. FIP uses a systematic process for determining the simulation requirements necessary to accomplish this specific objectives of each cockpit concept evaluation program.

As illustrated above, the Cockpit Integration Division is serious about controlling the cost of simulation. FIP determines specific cockpit simulation capabilities by analyzing the research to be undertaken in the particular cockpit. The analysis is transformed into simulation requirements and designs. The cockpits are then constructed from the appropriate hardware and software components, the composite of which meet the required level of sophistication.

MAGIC demonstrates a low cost, flexible cockpit simulator that provides a convenient mechanism for evaluating new display and control devices that could prove valuable to current and future Air Force cockpits. It's utilization of mass-produced, off-the-shelf peripherals helps control the cost of MAGIC's simulation environment while adding considerable flexibility.

MCS provides FIP with a vehicle to evaluate informational display formats and pilot aiding concepts in a simulated mission-oriented environment. Simulation costs for MCS are minimized by addressing the software development and maintenance costs. MCS's software consists of a set of loosely coupled, independently operating processes. Selected processes within this architecture can be substituted to accommodate requirements for new cockpit concept evaluations with minimal impact on overall simulation integrity.

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